

WAYS OF IMPROVING SERVICE QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *In this article, the basic principles of quality management, the fact that the consumer receives only a suitable product, the improvement of the management quality system, the product use conditions and whaton purpose workrelease, analysis of consumer requirements was considered.*

Keywords: *hotel industry, system, quality, product, consumer, service.*

Introduction. In the conditions of the market economy, the main task facing all enterprises is the production of competitive products and services. Therefore, products and services quality improve today's of the day important from issuesis considered Improving the quality of products and services is a strategic problem, and the stabilization of our country's economy depends on the solution of these problems. Quality improvement is necessary not only for the sake of profit, but also for society and its development.

The hotel industry is becoming one of the most promising types of activity in the market of Uzbekistan, and its development trend is considered as a source of additional income for entrepreneurs and the state budget. In the conditions of strong competition, creating and improving a system that ensures the improvement of the quality of hotel services has become an urgent issue for hotel managers. Therefore, the quality of services in the hotel business is a particularly relevant issue today.

It should be noted that the concept of quality in a very broad sense means meeting certain requirements and indicators. Quality is a set of properties and indicators that form the ability of a product (service) to meet specified or expected needs. The ability of the enterprise to achieve its goal, to ensure the competitiveness of the manufactured product, the management and organization procedure in it determined from the quality control procedure.

A quality management system is an agreed-upon work structure implemented in an enterprise that includes useful technical and management methods, provides the best and most convenient methods of interaction between people and machines, and also provides information and cost savings for quality.

As a result of the research, the following concept was emphasized, quality is a set of characteristics of services aimed at satisfying the needs of different levels determined by consumers. Quality allows customers to choose this service regardless of price. In the hotel industry, quality is a factor influencing customers' decision to use certain hotel services. There is a direct relationship between the quality of hotel services and their sales volume: a decrease in quality leads to a loss of customers. However, the creation of an effective quality management system is a difficult task without a thorough study and evaluation of the existing quality system in the researched hotel.

Basic principles of quality management:
the consumer must receive only a valid product;

management will be aimed at improving the quality system and preventing defects in production itself.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. A quantitative description of one or more characteristics of a service is called a quality indicator. The selection of quality indicators is the determination of the names of the quantitative description of the service characteristics that are part of the service quality and allow to assess its quality level. The justification of the choice of the names of quality indicators is carried out taking into account the following:

From the product use conditions and what on purpose production;

Analysis of consumer requirements;

Issues of service quality management;

The composition and structure of the described features;

Characteristics of services, such as imperceptibility, impermanence of quality, indistinguishable from material goods, and the inability to separate the service from the object, indicate that this evaluation includes complex issues and tasks. Quality management of services includes planning, organization of resources and organizational structure, and control of the process, which allows to achieve the intended goal in the field of quality. One of the most important tasks in managing the quality of services is the ability to correctly determine the level of customer expectations. Experiments show that in order to win in the competition, enterprises direct their activities to satisfy customers' needs at a high level, because the satisfaction of needs based on simple offers is enough for consumers to make a decision to choose other offers. Quality management includes three elements: quality management entities, quality management object and quality management mechanism (subject to object interaction). This process occurs on the basis of management functions. These functions include the company's quality policy, training and motivation of employees, relations with the external environment, effective decision-making by the hotel management. It should be noted that qualified staff and material and technical base play an important role in the provision of hotel services.

During the research and according to the practical experience of hotel operations, it becomes clear that the availability and condition of the material and technical base of hotels has a significant impact on the quality level. In this case, in order to increase the efficiency of the quality of hotel services, it is necessary to constantly develop them, taking into account the international requirements for their specific aspects and comfort.

To develop a quality system in hotel business enterprises, it is necessary to assess the state of the quality of services. The management of the hotel can create a working group that is engaged in this evaluation task. In this case, it is worth noting that consumer evaluation (their response, suggestions and comments, objections) is also important.

The questionnaire method can be used to determine the results of the evaluation of the quality of the services provided by consumers. We can include the following in the tasks of the special working group:

provide an objective assessment of the object;

development of alternative solutions to the problem;

effective decision making.

As mentioned above, one of the important features of services is their imperceptibility. In this situation, the entrepreneur's ability to transmit information about the quality of services to the consumer is limited. In this case, the consumer can use indirect information: opinions of relatives and acquaintances, various achievements (diplomas, certificates, etc.) achieved by the hospitality company. As a result, he may use the services of this hotel complex based on his personal decision and risk not being provided with the service he expected. It is in this situation that service quality management requires an alternative management system that deals with the provision and organization of services. Insufficient attention to the quality management process can destroy the economic efficiency of the hospitality enterprise. Effective management of a hospitality enterprise can also be considered at the level of rapidly developing marketing. The modern concept of marketing requires production and sales activities oriented to the final result, which focuses on profit while maintaining cordial relations and connections with consumers and members of society. This system envisages taking into account all three factors - the pursuit of profit, all the demands and wishes of consumers, as well as the interests of society.

Factors determining the future development of hospitality enterprises may be:

-effective marketing-oriented management that creates conditions for effective realization of products and services-implementation of an excellent quality system that ensures profitability and competitiveness of the enterprise.

Based on the international experience of the hotel business, it is worth mentioning that each foreign brand has its own corporate standard. hotel standard quality system control, personnel and continuous improvement of the service process. In addition, corporate standards are also related to the brand, which ensures the recognition of hotel facilities and positioning in certain market segments. Such hotels form a corporate culture. Corporate culture is considered as an integrated system of organizational values and beliefs of all employees and management. Corporate culture distinguishes each enterprise and organization from other enterprises and organizations

In conclusion, it can be said that the effective management of service quality has always been a relevant issue, but it began to develop further with the development of market relations. An important feature of services is their imperceptibility, which causes some problems in their management even today. The main task of hospitality enterprises is to provide high-quality services to consumers, as well as to ensure that they achieve certain benefits as a result of using services. In order to improve the quality of hotel services, we consider it appropriate to pay special attention to the following aspects of the management system:

- improvement of the material and technical base of hotels;
- organization of a special structure (working group) in the management structure that monitors quality and makes an impartial assessment of its condition;
- setting requirements for additional knowledge, qualifications and skills that ensure the professional level of employees;
- effective management of hotels based on marketing;
- existence of corporate culture and its development.

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